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“GRIM FATE”

In the dead of the night,
Lurks a danger hidden from sight.
Waiting for a prey to capture,
Feeding on fear and terror.

Stiletos strike the empty lane,
Echoed by her rising pain;
Hurried steps and ragged breath;
Broken whispers, fervent prayer.

Heartbeat drums a frantic cry,
Terror clouds her desperate eye;
Hope dissolves upon her face,
As Death reveals its dark embrace.

Then the night devours her scream,
Drowns it in a soundless hymn;
Indeed, fate sealed its dreadful role;
Darkness have claimed another soul.